

A Study of Female Identity Development in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Mistress of Spices*

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Abstract

*This paper scrutinizes the character of Tilo in Chitra Banderjee Divakaruni's *The Mistress of Spices* and evaluates how she develops herself in the course of her life. Tilo is an ageless wisewoman clothed in an ancient body. After a long apprenticeship to the "Old One," who tries to curb Tilo's arrogance in her own precocious ability, she becomes a "mistress of spices". Overcome by her attraction to Raven, Tilo yields to her own wishes rather than those of the spices. At this flouting of their rules, the spices themselves rise up against her, demanding that she has to choose between love and power. Tilo is forced to rethink her role as a healer beyond the simplistic split between her desire to help others and to help herself. This point is further explored through the female identity development theory of the famous feminist critic Carol Gilligan.*

Keywords: female identity development, Pre-conventional, Conventional, Post-conventional and psychic progression

'Female Identity Development' has been a vital discourse in the feminist studies. Whether women are professionals or non professionals, inspired by nature or nurture, a woman's understanding of her inner development certainly augments her self esteem and makes her to feel personhood. Perhaps this is one of the most important things that Feminism aspires. Many Feminist critics have worked on Female Identity Development and have successfully forwarded reasonable theories, the well known critics being Downing and Roush (1985), Carol Gilligan (1982) and a group of critics Belenky, Clinchy, Goldberger, and Tarule (1986/1997). Of these theories Carol Gilligan's moral development theory has been widely accepted. Carol Gilligan's book *In a Different Voice: Psychological theory and Women's Development* (1982), a path breaking venture challenges the male centered personality psychology of Sigmund Freud and Eric Erickson, also questions the moral development psychology postulated by Lawrence Kohlberg, her teacher. Gilligan proposes a stage theory of moral development for women, which indicates three levels of development, Pre-conventional, Conventional, and Post-conventional, with transitionary crossroads that are as significant as the levels and are relationally situated for women in their care for

and about others. Based on Carol Gilligan's moral development theory, the female protagonist in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Mistress of Spices* will be scrutinized to recognize her psychic progression.

The *Mistress of Spices* is a splendid novel. It is a beautifully crafted story of dreams, desires, hopes and expectations. Tilo, the protagonist of the novel was born in India and had a sad story. She is ugly and unwanted in a small village in India. She is discarded by her family for the sin of being born female.

They named me Nayantara star of the eye, but my parent's faces were heavy with fallen hope at another girl child...wrap her in old cloth, lay her face down on the floor...is creaming until they fed me milk from a white ass, perhaps that is why the words come to me so soon. Or was it the loneliness, the need rising angry in a dark girl left to wander the village unattended. (7-8)

She is gifted with predicting the future and other supernatural powers. People from every walk of life praise her and the pirates come to know of her. They carry her through the burning village. She becomes the queen of sea pirates who name her Bhagyavathi. But the snakes help her to escape from the place. She wants to go to the island of spices. When Nayantara has been driving with pirates on the sea, she throws herself in discovering the magical island of spices. Then she has been adopted by the old, fraud ancient figure and given training to use the spices for healing the pain. After training each apprentice choose a new name. That is not only symbolic of their new identity in new world.

To her the transition between the stages is triggered by changes in the sense of self rather than the changes in the cognitive capability. Level I, Pre-conventional stage is the 'Orientation to Individual Survival' where one is oriented toward self-interest, survival and preservation of self. Nayantara chooses the name Tilotamma. Every spice has medical remedy, connecting on the uses of "til" and meaning of "Tilotama" she says:

Til is the sesame seed, under the sway of planet venus, gold brown as though just touched by flame. The flower of which is so small and straight and pointed that mothers pray for their girl children to have noses shaped liked it. Til which ground into paste with sandalwood cures diseases of heart and liver, till which fried in its oil restores luster when one host lost interest in life. I will be Tilotama, the essence of til, life giver, restorer of health and hope. (42)

The old one accepts the name, as the name Tilo on her part stand for the most beautiful apsara of rain at God Indira's court. At the same time, the old one warns her not to give her heart to anyone like the court dancer of Indira. Tilotamma is warned by Brahma not to give her heart to man but only to the dance. Tilo has to accept her lot as Tilotamma accepted it in Indira's court. As a young girl, Tilo is initiated as one of several young Mistresses of Spices by the First Mother, who warns the girls about certain rules they must follow, or face dire consequences. They are instructed never to leave their respective stores all around the world, physically touch the skin of the people they meet, or use the great and incomprehensible strength and power of the Spices to their own ends.

The first transition, from Level I to Level II, is identified as 'From Selfishness to Responsibility'. Here the woman develops attachment and connection to others, with an ability to see within herself the potential for social acceptance/approval. She learns to integrate responsibility and care into moral decision-making.

Tilo, an immigrant from India, is a shopkeeper, an unusually strong clairvoyant, and a chosen Mistress of Spices. The spices she gives to her customers help them to satisfy their certain needs and desires, such as "sandalwood to dispel painful memories; black cumin seed to protect against evil eye." Tilo ends up in the San Francisco Bay Area in a store called "Spice Bazaar". Tilo's

customers include Haroun, a cab driver, a grandfather are dealt an American-born granddaughter Geeta, Kwesi, a man trying to impress his girlfriend and Jagjit, a teenager trying to fit in at school.

In Level II, the 'Conventional stage'– 'Goodness as Self-Sacrifice', a woman develops greater engagement with others. Her survival now is based on social acceptance and she may give up her own judgment in order to be accepted. She may also experience disequilibrium over conflict between her self-definition and her care for others. The journey of Tilo is a novice from the spices island to America as a mistress of spice store involves transformation. As a mistress of spices she has to follow the rules which have been instructed to her by the Old one. She finds herself in the store after she has entered the Shampati's fire. "Shell within shell, and in most of all my heart beating like a bird" (125). She also notices that apart from the walls of the store that protected her, the spices also form a shield around her. Not only the walls and spices but her wrinkled aged body shields her from outside interference. But despite all these barriers her heart is like a bird within. The word 'bird' conveys her yearning to be free in spite of her willful acceptance to be a mistress, if her freedom is curtailed, it saddens her.

At the end of the story, Tilo thinks that because of her supernatural power she has to forget her personal life and desire. Her life takes a turn one day, when a handsome man on a motorcycle crashes outside her store. Tilo tends to his injuries while trying to ignore their strong mutual romantic attraction to each other. Her life changes when he touches her and they begin to fall truly, madly in love. Tilo falls in love with handsome American Raven and decides to transform in to a young woman to fulfil her desires. But the Spices are suddenly angry and jealous, and things soon start to go sour in her relationships with her other customers. Haroun gets in an accident, Geeta's family situation does not improve, Jagjit falls in with the wrong crowd at school, and Kwesi's girlfriend breaks up with him. Doug comes to meet her that night and sadly tells her that his Native American-born mother has died. Then she is in dilemma whether to be selfless or selfish.

The second transition occurs from Level II to Level III and is called 'From Goodness to Truth'. Here the woman moves from self-sacrifice for conformity to a new inner judgment. As she begins to see her own needs as truth and not as selfishness, she begins to take responsibility for decisions. At the end of the novel Tilo, becomes Maya, the young woman, She has left her job as mistress of spices. She says: "I who now have only myself to hold me up". (MS-317). She found her new identity and new home through an act of cultural translation. Divakaruni succeeds in presenting the consciousness of South Asian diasporic women and the process of identity formation.

Tilo recognizes that the source of these misfortunes is her breaking of the rules. The first other comes to her in a vision and scolds her for choosing Doug over the Spices. She vows that he will return to india, and posts a notice about a closing sale. She goes all out to help her customers one last time and tells the Spices that she will spend just one night with Doug, and then she will give herself utterly to them. She closes the store and goes off with Doug for the night. After a sweet night of romantic, passionate love-making, she leaves him a note that she must leave and cannot return, but that will always truly, madly and deeply love him forever. Then she goes back to the store and sets the Spices on fire, with her at the center of the flames, as sign of eternal servitude and slavery to the mystical Spices.

In Level III, Post-Conventional stage, 'The Morality of Nonviolence', the woman has a new respect for the self, with no dichotomy between selfishness and responsibility to others any longer. She balances a moral equivalency between self and others, between survival and care. Gilligan states that a morality of nonviolence is then extended to self and others. Doug comes searching for her, and finds the store devastated. But Tilo has not been burned. She is still alive. There is no sign of fire, but there has been an earthquake. Since she demonstrates her willingness to give up everything for the Spices, she can have everything she desires and the spices will never desert her

again. Doug agrees to help her rebuild the store, and she happily reunites with him. Their romantic relationship blossoms again as strong and pure as ever. Tilo seems to exemplify Carol Gilligan's 'post-conventional stage', the third stage of her theory of moral development as she shows no difference between self-interest and responsibility.

Tilo is forced to rethink her role as a healer beyond the simplistic split between her desire to help others and to help herself. In doing so, she conjures up a new American identity. Tilo can be compared to Jasmine of Bharati Mukherjee. Jasmine revolves around the Protagonist with various identities in the confused world as Jyoti, Jazzy, Jane and Jase. She is constantly made to face one name or another, one culture or another and one challenge or another throughout her tiring journey of life from Hasnapur to Iowa. The identity crisis is reflected in Tilo's journey of life as a foreteller, as the queen of pirates, as a novice, as a mistress and as a lover. She goes through four distinct incarnations in different bodies such as Nayantara, Bhagyavathi, Tilo and Maya.

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